

A machine learning study of the effect of thrombolysis on outcome at discharge in the UK stroke registry: How does benefit compare with clinical trials?

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Abstract

Background and Purpose: Thrombolysis has been shown to reduce disability after acute ischaemic stroke in randomised trials. Our study sought to compare the benefit from thrombolysis observed in a comprehensive national stroke registry with that expected from the clinical trials.

Methods: Data from a total of 168,347 ischaemic stroke patients who attended one of 118 emergency stroke hospitals in England and Wales from 2016 to 2021 were extracted from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP). We constructed a machine learning model, designed to isolate the effect of thrombolysis, using explainable machine learning (XGBoost with SHAP).

Results: Thrombolysis was found to be associated with a statistically significant improvement in the odds of achieving a better outcome (mRS threshold). Regression analysis predicted a maximum 2.5-fold improvement in odds of achieving mRS 0-1, with a decline to no treatment effect at 5 hours 28 minutes post-onset.

Conclusions: Our results confirm a beneficial effect of thrombolysis in a large prospective national stroke registry, and align closely with meta-analyses of clinical trials of thrombolysis both in terms of magnitude of effect and decline over time. This work also demonstrates the potential to apply explainable machine learning to observational data to assist in understanding how clinical trials are implemented in real-world settings.

1 Introduction

Stroke remains one of the top three global causes of death and disability¹. Despite reductions in age-standardised rates of stroke, ageing populations are driving an increase in the absolute number of strokes¹.

Thrombolysis with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator, can significantly reduce disability after ischaemic stroke, provided it is given in the first few hours after stroke onset². Despite thrombolysis being of proven benefit in ischaemic stroke, use of thrombolysis varies significantly both between and within European countries³. In England and Wales the prospective Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP; the national stroke registry) reported that in 2021/22, 20 years after the original European Medicines Agency licencing of alteplase for acute ischaemic stroke, thrombolysis rates varied from 1% to 28% of emergency stroke admissions between hospitals⁴, with a median rate of 10.4% and an

inter-quartile range of 8%-13%, against a 2019 NHS England long term plan that 20% of patients with stroke should be receiving thrombolysis⁵.

Studies have shown that the reasons for low and varying thrombolysis use are multifactorial. Organizational factors can reduce the effectiveness of thrombolysis administration³, and clinicians can have varying attitudes to use of thrombolysis⁶.

We have previously used clinical pathway simulation and machine learning modeling of the variation in thrombolysis use between stroke teams to establish in England and Wales that the largest contributor to variation in thrombolysis practice was the attitudes of clinicians to the use of thrombolysis, particularly in ‘less than ideal’ patients^{7;8}.

In addressing such persisting uncertainty among clinicians, it is important to test that the benefit of thrombolysis predicted in clinical trials is being observed in the context of real-world stroke care. Various observational studies have provided further support for the effectiveness of thrombolysis^{9;10}. None of these studies, however, were able to investigate the relationship between time-to-thrombolysis and effectiveness compared to the clinical trial meta-analyses, and none were in a specific context where clinical registry data is used to drive change.

With the prospective collection of clinical data into SSNAP for all emergency stroke admissions in all hospitals in England and Wales, and with the power of new explainable machine learning techniques, our aim was to build a model of stroke outcomes, perform a large scale analysis of the benefit of thrombolysis in practice in a UK setting, and to compare the relationship between time-to-thrombolysis and effectiveness with clinical trial results.

2 Methods

2.1 Data

Data were retrieved for 168,347 emergency ischaemic stroke admissions to hospitals in England and Wales for six calendar years, 2016–2021 inclusive, obtained from the national stroke registry SSNAP. Further details may be found in the supplementary material.

2.2 Machine learning models

We trained a set of six independent XGBoost models¹¹ to predict the likelihood of an ischaemic stroke patient attaining any given mRS threshold at discharge (where achieving a lower threshold is better). The model of $mRS \leq 5$ also provides a model of survival vs. death. The results from the test set for the model fitted on the first k-fold split was used to report the relationships between feature values and their contribution to the predictions.

Code, and full results, for the machine learning work may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/thrombolysis_clinical_trials_ml_paper. Further details of method development may be found in the supplementary material.

2.3 Feature selection and model building

The complete available data set contained 57 features that described patient demographic and clinical characteristics, the acute stroke pathway, the use/time of thrombolysis, and the stroke team attended. We have previously identified features that influence the choice to use thrombolysis¹². For the current work, we identified the features that influence patient outcome and, after discussions with clinicians, combined the two sets of features (on use of thrombolysis, and outcome after stroke) into a proposed model with seven features that would better isolate the effect of thrombolysis on outcome.

2.4 Model accuracy

For each of the six machine learning models, we report the model accuracy measured using 5-fold cross validation where the data is split into 5 different 80:20 train/test splits with each patient being in one, and only one, test set.

2.5 SHapley Additive exPlanation (SHAP) values

SHAP values quantify the contribution of each feature to the model’s prediction of a good discharge outcome¹³. Because SHAP values are expressed on the log-odds scale, they are additive and therefore more suitable than probabilities for assessing the contribution of individual features to the final prediction. Separate SHAP analyses were performed for each of the six machine learning models, corresponding to the six mRS thresholds. A positive SHAP value indicates that a feature increases the likelihood of reaching the mRS threshold (better outcome), whereas a negative SHAP value indicates that a feature decreases it. SHAP values can be examined both locally, at the individual patient level, and globally, across the cohort, to identify general patterns in how patient, pathway, and hospital characteristics are associated with discharge outcomes.

2.6 Counterfactual treatment: What if patients had not received thrombolysis?

After constructing a model (splitting data 80% training, 20% test) to isolate the effect of thrombolysis from confounding variables, we used counterfactuals for each patient in the test set who had received thrombolysis, to assess the contribution that thrombolysis made on the likelihood of achieving any particular mRS threshold at discharge. The counterfactual result was achieved by running the same model, but changing the patient to mimic not receiving thrombolysis.

The predicted contribution of thrombolysis to the achievement of an excellent outcome (mRS 0–1) was estimated by the difference in SHAP thrombolysis values between when thrombolysis was administered and the counterfactual scenario of not receiving thrombolysis. To model decay of thrombolysis benefit with treatment delay, we fitted a linear regression of estimated thrombolysis benefit (log-odds shift for achieving mRS 0–1) on time from onset to thrombolysis, excluding patients treated after 300 minutes. We defined an excellent outcome as mRS 0–1 to align with the definition used in the clinical-trial meta-analysis by Emberson et al.². Analyses were performed in three thrombolysed cohorts: (1) all ischaemic strokes ($n = 6,897$), (2) severe ischaemic strokes (NIHSS ≥ 11 ; $n = 2,897$), and (3) mild-to-moderate ischaemic strokes (NIHSS 0–10; $n = 4,000$).

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive statistics

168,347 patients (with onset-to-scan of within 255 minutes) attended 118 hospitals with total stroke admissions per hospital ranging from 358 to 4,559, and with hospital thrombolysis rates ranging from 5.9% to 39.2%. Of the 133,516 patients who did not receive thrombolysis, their range of disability at discharge was: 12% mRS 0, 33% mRS 0-1, 52% mRS 0-2, 69% mRS 0-3, 82% mRS 0-4, and 88% mRS 0-5 at discharge. Of the 34,831 patients who received thrombolysis, their range of disability at discharge was: 15% mRS 0, 35% mRS 0-1, 54% mRS 0-2, 69% mRS 0-3, 81% mRS 0-4, and 86% mRS 0-5. Table 1 shows further descriptive statistics for patients who received or did not receive thrombolysis. 30.7% had six month follow-up assessment of mRS. On average mRS at 6 months is very close to mRS at discharge (0.12 higher), but there was variation at individual patient level: 31% had no change between discharge and 6 month follow-up, 73% had no change or a change of 1 mRS band, and 27% had a change of two or more mRS bands. Those with discharge mRS of 2-4 were more likely to improve, rather than worsen. Further descriptive statistics are provided in the Supplemental Material.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for patients receiving or not receiving thrombolysis.

	Thrombolysis given			Thrombolysis not given		
	n	Mean (StdDev)	Median (IQR)	n	Mean (StdDev)	Median (IQR)
Age	41163	72.3 (13.6)	72.5 (62.5-82.5)	315941	74.5 (13.3)	77.5 (67.5-82.5)
Infarction	41163	1 (NA)	NA	315941	0.86 (NA)	NA
Stroke severity	41163	11.0 (7.1)	9 (5-16)	315941	6.6 (7.6)	4 (2-8)
Prior disability	41163	0.71 (1.17)	0 (0-1)	315941	1.08 (1.39)	0 (0-2)
Male	41163	0.56 (NA)	NA	315941	0.53 (NA)	NA
Onset known	41163	0.99 (NA)	NA	315941	0.63 (NA)	NA
Precise onset known	41163	0.80 (NA)	NA	315941	0.28 (NA)	NA
Onset during sleep	41163	0.01 (NA)	NA	315941	0.15 (NA)	NA
Onset to arrival time	40583	102 (53)	90 (66-128)	198105	57 (1115)	250 (112-713)
Arrive by ambulance	41161	0.92 (NA)	NA	315934	0.77 (NA)	NA
Arrival to scan time	41163	23 (20)	19 (11-29)	315941	217 (2016)	61 (26-149)
Congestive heart failure	41163	0.04 (NA)	NA	315941	0.05 (NA)	NA
Hypertension	41163	0.51 (NA)	NA	315941	0.55 (NA)	NA
Atrial fibrillation (Afib)	41163	0.12 (NA)	NA	315941	0.19 (NA)	NA
New afib diagnosis	24485	0.11 (NA)	NA	172727	0.06 (NA)	NA
Diabetes	41163	0.17 (NA)	NA	315941	0.22 (NA)	NA
Prior stroke or TIA	41163	0.20 (NA)	NA	315941	0.26 (NA)	NA
Afib antiplatelet	41163	0.03 (NA)	NA	315940	0.03 (NA)	NA
Afib anticoagulant	30128	0.04 (NA)	NA	237923	0.19 (NA)	NA
Afib vit k anticoagulant	41163	0.01 (NA)	NA	315940	0.03 (NA)	NA
Afib DOAC anticoagulant	41163	0.01 (NA)	NA	315940	0.08 (NA)	NA
Scan to thrombolysis time	41163	37 (29)	31 (19-47)	NA	NA	NA
Thrombectomy	41163	0.06 (NA)	NA	315941	0.01 (NA)	NA
Arrival to thrombectomy time	2591	201 (179)	171 (114-233)	1752	249 (278)	172 (104-269)

3.2 Feature selection and proposed model

Features affecting choice of thrombolysis have previously been described¹². Details of feature selection for outcome prediction are detailed in the supplementary material. Based also on the selection of characteristics for the prediction of the outcome, we developed figure 1 as a proposed schematic of the factors that affect the use of thrombolysis and the factors that directly affect the outcome. This proposed causal model is based on features identified as affecting outcome or propensity to use thrombolysis, correlations present in the data, known temporal relationships in the data, and clinical review.

In order to isolate the effect of thrombolysis appropriately, we predicted outcome based on use/time to thrombolysis, and 6 factors identified as confounding variables (affecting both outcome directly and propensity to use thrombolysis).

1. Onset to thrombolysis time
2. Prior disability level: mRS before stroke
3. Stroke severity: NIHSS on arrival
4. Stroke team: Hospital first attended
5. Age: As midpoint of 5 year age bands
6. Atrial fibrillation diagnosis: Patient had a diagnosis of atrial fibrillation either on arrival or diagnosed during admission
7. Precise onset known: Onset time recorded was recorded as being precise time (as opposed to a best estimate)

3.3 Model accuracy

With these seven input features, the overall accuracy ranged from 77.6% to 89.7% in the six mRS disability level models (the standard deviation of accuracy across the 5 k-fold train/test splits ranged from 0.1% to 0.2%). This

Figure 1: A Directed Acyclic Graph (‘DAG’) showing the proposed relationships in propensity to use thrombolysis and outcome after stroke with or without thrombolysis.

represented between 95-98% of the accuracy that is obtained with all the features as inputs. ROC-AUC ranged from 0.852 to 0.893 across the six models (standard deviation of the ROC-AUC across the 5 k-folds ranged from 0.001 to 0.002). Results were reproducible across the 5 k-folds, so subsequent analysis was performed on the first k-fold split.

3.4 SHAP patterns

SHAP values were calculated for each feature for each patient, showing how each value affects the log odds of achieving any particular mRS threshold at discharge. For each patient in the test set we extracted SHAP values for each feature with its corresponding feature value. Figure 2a shows the relationship between feature values and the odds of a patient having an excellent outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge (a positive SHAP value contributes to an increased likelihood, and a negative SHAP value contributes to a reduced likelihood). We found that low prior disability, lower stroke severity, younger age, receiving thrombolysis (and receiving it sooner after onset), and having no diagnosis of atrial fibrillation contributed to a patient more likely having an excellent outcome at discharge. Figure 2b focusses on the feature *onset to thrombolysis time*, and its effect on reaching any disability threshold. As time from onset to thrombolysis increased, the beneficial effect of thrombolysis decayed. For thresholds up to, and including, mRS 3, the median effect of thrombolysis remained positive, compared to not receiving thrombolysis, up until the maximum time of 720 minutes. For thresholds of mRS 4 and upwards, the median effect of thrombolysis became negative at longer onset-to-thrombolysis times. This was especially apparent in how thrombolysis changed the overall odds of survival (mRS 0-5) where the median effect of thrombolysis became negative from about 155 minutes. Later thrombolysis may therefore increase the proportion of patients attaining mRS 0-3, but at the cost of some reduction in overall survival. Earlier thrombolysis improved the odds of survival. Figure 2c shows the contribution from attending a specific hospital to predicting whether the patient achieved each mRS threshold at discharge. As the mRS threshold becomes more inclusive of higher disability levels, the effect of the hospital attended had a reduced contribution. In other words, the hospital attended made a greater contribution to variation in outcome with thrombolysis for patients with lesser degrees of disability after treatment.

3.5 Counterfactuals - what if patients had not received thrombolysis?

Using the counterfactual results for all of the patients in the first k-fold test set that received thrombolysis within 300 minutes from stroke onset ($n = 6,796$), table 2 shows a linear regression fitted to the shift in the contribution of thrombolysis towards having an excellent outcome at discharge (mRS 0-1) with respect to the onset to thrombolysis

a) The relationship between feature values and the prediction of whether a patient will be discharged mRS 0-1

b) The relationship between onset to thrombolysis time and the prediction of whether a patient will be discharged at each mRS threshold.

c) The contribution of attending a specific hospital to the prediction of whether a patient will be discharged at each mRS threshold.

Figure 2: The relationship between feature values and SHAP values in predicting whether a patient is discharged at each mRS threshold. Violin plots show the distribution of SHAP values across the patient population for each feature value, with the mid-line showing the median SHAP value.

time. We found, for all treated patients, that the effect of thrombolysis had declined to zero at 328 minutes, and the effect from thrombolysis was improving log odds of being discharged mRS 0-1 by 0.90 if it were, theoretically, given at the time of stroke onset. We observed that the maximum theoretical effect of thrombolysis (if given at time of stroke onset) was greater for the severe stroke group (1.048 log odds) than the mild-moderate stroke group (0.771 log odds). However the effect of thrombolysis declined more rapidly in the severe stroke group, reaching no effect at 314 minutes for severe stroke patients, compared to 351 minutes for mild-moderate stroke patients.

Table 2: Linear regression of the relationship between onset-to-thrombolysis time (OTT) and the improvement in log-odds of achieving an excellent outcome (mRS 0-1), stratified by stroke severity.

Ischaemic stroke type	Variables	Estimate	std err	Low 95% confidence	High 95% confidence	t	P> t
All	Constant	0.901	0.007	0.888	0.915	132.5	0.000
	OTT (min) coef	-0.0027	4.04e-05	-0.003	-0.003	-68.1	0.000
Severe NIHSS 11+	Constant	1.048	0.011	1.026	1.069	96.7	0.000
	OTT (mins) coef	-0.0033	6.67e-05	-0.003	-0.003	-50.0	0.000
Mild-moderate (NIHSS 0-10)	Constant	0.771	0.008	0.755	0.786	97.6	0.000
	OTT (mins) coef	-0.0022	4.57e-05	-0.002	-0.002	-48.1	0.000

Figure 3: Linear regression of thrombolysis contribution to excellent outcome (mRS 0–1) at discharge as a function of onset-to-thrombolysis time (OTT) in patients treated within 300 minutes. Left: all treated stroke patients ($n = 6,796$); Middle: severe stroke patients (NIHSS 11+; $n = 2,856$); Right: mild-moderate stroke patients (NIHSS 0–10; $n = 3,940$).

4 Discussion

In this study we have built explainable machine learning models based on a comprehensive prospective national stroke registry capable of predicting outcome, at any given disability threshold, with high precision. The models were constructed considering the which features affect both the use and outcome of thrombolysis, in order to isolate the effect of thrombolysis and to understand the effect of thrombolysis in the real world.

The most influential factors that favoured achieving any given disability threshold were lower pre-stroke disability, lower stroke severity, younger age, and the use and speed of thrombolysis. The hospital attended also had an effect on achieving any disability threshold, although that effect was reduced among the more severely affected patients with increasing disability at discharge. This could be due to 1) some hospitals discharging patients earlier with more disability e.g. those with more community rehabilitation available, 2) effects of other hospital treatments on outcomes e.g. better/worse stroke unit care, or 3) hospitals assessing disability at discharge differently. From our model we cannot speculate further, but by including stroke team in the model we can adjust the model for these effects, thereby allowing a clearer view of other patient or organisational features, including use and time of thrombolysis, affecting outcome.

Using a large, inclusive real-world model enables counterfactual prediction of outcomes with and without thrombolysis for any patient. Here, we focused on predicting outcomes without thrombolysis among patients who actually received it, allowing estimation of the treatment effect in treated patients. SHAP values were used to isolate the contribution of thrombolysis to the model prediction. SHAP values provide the contribution of any given input to the model to the models' final prediction (e.g. of the patient being discharged mRS 0-1), and the model allowed us to isolate the the effect of thrombolysis from other patient features, and run counterfactual analysis of what would the outcome have been if a patient had not received thrombolysis (when they had received it). We found thrombolysis improved the odds of being at or below any given disability threshold, but the effect of thrombolysis was reduced, and decayed to no-effect sooner, for outcomes of $mRS \leq 5$ (survival). We found that the effect of thrombolysis was present for both mild-moderate and severe strokes, but with a larger effect in severe strokes. The findings from this study were remarkably similar to the meta-analysis of clinical trials², which extrapolate back to a 0.69 log odds improvement (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.0) of being mRS 0-1 at stroke onset, with no effect after 378 minutes (6.3 hours). Our maximum theoretical improvement in log odds of achieving mRS 0-1 was a little higher at 0.90 (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.5), with a decline to no-effect at 328 minutes (5.5 hours), indicating a a little faster decline in effectiveness with time in our observational real-world study when compared to the original randomised data. This is likely to be due to the licencing conditions for alteplase, in that the meta-analysis included randomised trials out to 6 hours from stroke onset², whereas the overwhelming majority of patients treated in the UK over the six-year study period were restricted to guideline-based eligibility within 4.5 hours¹⁴.

The clinical significance of this work is that we have confirmed the net benefit of thrombolysis in a very large prospective national stroke registry that encompasses patients outside the strictly defined eligibility of the original randomised trials, and used sophisticated machine learning with SHAP to isolate the effect of thrombolysis from other patient

characteristics that influence outcomes. This provides significant reassurance that in real-world clinical practice, the anticipated benefits of thrombolysis are being delivered in the context of the stroke system in England and Wales, even when treatment is implemented in a wider spectrum of patients than those represented in the randomized trials.

In summary, applying explainable machine learning to an observational data set demonstrated that the effectiveness of thrombolysis in the *real world* appears to be at least as good as the clinical trials indicated. Our results should give stroke clinicians more confidence that the beneficial effect of thrombolysis is seen in real treatment populations. The size of the observational data set allows for more detailed analysis of the benefit of thrombolysis in subgroups of patients.

4.1 Study limitations

Though we are using a very large data set, our study necessarily has some limitations:

- Our results are specific to real-world use of thrombolysis in hospitals in England and Wales. They are not intended to be generalisable outside of this area.
- A group of more severely affected stroke patients who proceeded to receive thrombectomy has been excluded from the analysis, although during the six year study period endovascular intervention was increasing from a low base in the UK, and increased from 0.7% to 2.0% of all stroke.
- We have used the mRS at hospital discharge as our primary outcome, whereas the trials used the mRS at 90 days. On average across the patient population stroke outcomes are similar at 3 months¹⁵ and at 6 months (our own analysis) but individual patients may improve or worsen, though those discharged with mRS 2-4 are more likely to improve than worsen. Though we do not include discharge timing directly in the model, by using stroke team identifiers, the model should be adjusted for differences that are due to between-hospital variation in discharge practices, such as timing of discharge.
- Our results are based on data from 2016 to 2021. Since then practices may have changed, such as more use of tenecteplase rather than alteplase, more use of thrombectomy, and increased use of anti-platelet therapy. When interpreting results, this study should be seen in the context of largely studying alteplase. Further studies, with more recent data, should be performed for an analysis of more recent treatment regimes.
- The DAG was constructed internally within the team without external validation and was based on routine (observed) data meaning that we did not include unobserved variables. Though we have sought the best isolation of the effect of thrombolysis that we can, it is possible that unknown or unmeasured confounders may be skewing results.

4.2 Further work

Considering recent suggestions that thrombolysis should not be used in mild stroke^{16;17}, a more in-depth study of the observed effect of thrombolysis mild stroke, combining machine learning with causal inference methods such as propensity-score adjustment or target trial emulation, would add to the evidence base around in this contentious group of patients. Additionally the methods described here could be applied to looking at level of benefit in other subgroups of patients (e.g. where prior disability exists). Qualitative research with clinicians involved in thrombolysis decisions would provide an opportunity to examine our causal assumptions. Elicitation of clinician views would also provide an opportunity to examine whether any unobserved variables should be included to provide a more comprehensive DAG.

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Author Contributions

The study was designed and conducted by KP, MA, MJ and AL. Methods and results were reviewed and refined by PM, RE, MK, JD, JS, EK. Clinical review was by MJ, AB. PPIE input was by LF and LA.

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Informed consent and Ethics

As we are using anonymised secondary data, collected for national audit, individual consent is not required. SSNAP has approval under section 251 of the NHS Health and Social Care Act (2006) to collect patient level data on the first six months of patient care (ECC 6- 02(FT3)/2012), without requiring individual patient consent. Access to SSNAP data is managed by the UK Healthcare Quality Improvement Partnership (HQIP), with this project being approved by HQIP (HQIP303). More information on SSNAPs use of patient data may be found at: <https://www.strokeaudit.org/SupportFiles/Documents/Patient-area-documents/Fair-processingstatement-for-patients-v7-0.aspx>

As we are using anonymised secondary data, collected for national audit, used for service evaluation and improvement, no ethical approval is required (confirmed using the NHS Health Research Authority decision aid: <https://www.hra-decisiontools.org.uk/ethics/>).

Guarantor

The corresponding author, Michael Allen, is the guarantor of the paper (PI on the NIHR project funding).